

Questions, Comments and Answers following the presentation

*A very high signal-to-noise spectrum towards μ Col
Jonathan Smoker*

Lupton: Why are you using a validity date for calibration products rather than asking if the calibration data is stable?

In the end I used flatfields from plus and minus 3 months, several hundred flatfields. Shifts in the cross dispersion affecting the flatfields were taken into account by reducing the extraction length over which we used the master flatfield. This worked fine. For the general question see the response by Reinhard.

Hanuschik: Comment: the UVES flats record, amongst other things, the spectral format, which is to some extent temperature dependent. The validity timescale for the flats (~ 3 days) is motivated by this temperature-dependance.

Ballester: At high S/N, the systematic errors introduced by optimal extraction must be evaluated especially in the overlap areas.

For the reduction we found that the average extraction gave better results in terms of S/N ratio.